

Notes

CNDO/2 Calculations on the Percentage of cis-trans Isomers in Some Thioamides

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THE cis-isomer predominates in secondary thioamides compared to the corresponding amides. This may be due to the large size of the sulphur atom in comparison to oxygen atom. Recently, Walter and Kubersky^{1,2} have carried out extensive spectroscopic studies on thioamides and thioformanilides. They have studied the electronic, steric and conformational properties, intramolecular hydrogen bonding and cis-trans isomerism in thioamides and thioformanilides from the frequencies and the relative intensities of the NH-stretching vibration bands of primary and secondary thioamides in carbon-tetrachloride solutions. In the present studies, we have tested the validity of CNDO/2 method^{3,4} and of the equation (I)

$$\frac{N_{trans}}{N_{cis}} = \exp(-\Delta E/RT) \quad \dots (I)$$

$$\% \text{ of trans-isomer} = \frac{N_{trans}}{N_{cis} + N_{trans}} \times 10^2 \quad \dots (II)$$

for determining the cis-trans ratio in thioamides. In equation (I), ΔE is the energy difference between the cis and trans isomers. The value of ΔE was calculated by CNDO/2 method^{3,4} and the results are given in Table I. Using $R = 1.9869 \text{ cal/}^\circ\text{K/mole}$ and at $T = 25^\circ (298^\circ\text{K})$, the percentage of trans isomer determined by equation (II) is given in Table I.

TABLE I: PERCENTAGE OF CIS-TRANS ISOMERS IN SOME THIOAMIDES

Molecule	ΔE (Kcal/mole)	% of trans isomer	
		Calc.	Obs. (^{1,2})
N-Methylthioformamide	-1.40	91	93.5
N-Ethylthioformamide	-1.22	88	88.0
N-Propylthioformamide	-1.22	88	86.5
N-Isopropylthioformamide	-1.06	84	79.5
N-Butylthioformamide	-0.84	81	87.0
N-Isobutylthioformamide	-0.78	79	78.0

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It is quite evident from Table I that there is a good agreement between the experimental and theoretical values and hence the validity of the CNDO/2 method and equation (I) for determining the cis-trans ratios in these systems is established.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Co(II) with Ethylene diamine & Propylene diamine

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COBALT(II) yields Co(II) Pyrrolidone which on further coordination with ethylene diamine and propylene diamine gives mixed ligand complexes. The complexes after isolation and purification have been studied and their structures elucidated using spectro photometric and magnetic data supported by conductivity and molecular weight measurements. General methods for preparation have been discussed in literature¹⁻³.

Experimental data of complexes have been summarised in the table given below. The calculated values of percentages of Co, N and mol.wts., on basis of elemental analysis have been shown in parentheses against their respective experimental values.

Results and Discussion

Visible spectral data of complexes and molar extinction coefficient values support the tetrahedral structure of complexes^{4,5}. Magnetic moment values lie in the range 4.4-4.8 B.M. which is the reported range for tetrahedral Co(II) complexes^{6,7}.

In pyrrolidone molecule there are two possibilities of coordination, one from N atom and the other from carbonyl group with the opening of the double bond. Structural limitations do not allow the attachment of Co(II) with C=O group. According to Lewis concept 'N' with a lone pair of electrons possesses greater possibility of coordination with metal atom. From i.r. data it has been noted that the C=O

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TABLE 1

Sr. No.	Complex	% Co(II)	Analysis % N	Mol. wt.	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (nm)
1.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ · 2H ₂ O]	22.29 (22.14)	10.32(10.68)	—	4.45	—
2.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ endn]	20.12 (20.05)	19.32(19.50)	304 (287)	4.69	430 (E = 14.64), 560, 835
3.	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ pndn]	19.28 (19.40)	09.59(09.30)	309 (302)	4.70	435 (E = 17.22), 560, 740

Calculated values are in parantheses.

TABLE 2—(INFRA RED ASSIGNMENTS)

	endn	pndn	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ endn]	[Co(II) (Pyr) ₂ pndn]
N-H Stretch	3505 msp	3495 mbr	3440 mbr	3375 sbr
N-H bending	1655 msp	1650 msp	1635 mbr	1625 wbr
C-N Stretch	1225 ssp	1215 msp	1155 msp	1140 ssp
C = O Stretch	—	—	1590 mbr	1625 mbr

Abbreviation : endn = ethylenediamine, pndn = propylenediamine, pyr = 2-pyrrolidone, m = medium, s = strong, sp = sharp, br = broad.

frequency remains unaltered on coordination ; on the other hand the N-H bending vibration which usually occurs in the range 1500–1590 cm⁻¹ disappears on coordination, indicating that the coordination take place through nitrogen atom only.

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Flavonoid Constituents of *Lycopersicon esculentum*

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LYCOSPERSICON esculentum belongs to the family Solanaceae and is rich in vitamins A and C¹.

The defatted seeds of *L. esculentum* were first extracted with acidulated (1 N HCl) methanol and the study of the methanolic extract containing anthocyanins has already been communicated. Thereafter the seeds were extracted with cold acetone. The acetone extract after concentration under reduced pressure was treated with ether and the ethereal extract on concentration yielded a yellow solid mass which on paper chromatography and TLC

examination showed the presence of two ferric positive spots. The yellow solid mass was chromatographed on a column of silica gel and eluted with benzene : ethylacetate [(i) (75 : 25, V/V), (ii) (15 : 85, V/V)]. The eluate (i) gave compound X and eluate (ii) gave compound Y respectively.

Compound X was crystallised from a mixture of acetone : methanol (1 : 1), when light yellow crystals, m.p. 316°, C, 59.58; H, 3.33%, m/e = 302, molecular formula C₁₅H₁₀O₇, acetyl derivative, m.p. 198°–99°, were obtained. Co-chromatographic examination and mixed m.p. determination with authentic sample of quercetin confirmed it to be quercetin.

Compound Y crystallised from methanol (m.p. 274°–75°), responded to usual colour tests for flavonoids. It gave no positive Molisch's test indicating it to be a free flavone and not a glycoside. It was identified as Kaempferol by co-chromatography, mixed m.p. determination and superimposable spectral studies.

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A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycine with some Metal Ions. Part XXI. Cu(II) and Hg(II) Chelates of N-Benzenesulphonyl L(–) Aspartic Acid and N-Benzenesulphonyl L(+) Glutamic Acid

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IN a previous communication¹, complex compounds formed by the ligand N-benzenesulphonyl L(–) aspartic acid (R₂H₂) have been reported. Now a